

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The Status of Learning Environment in Malinao district

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Abstract

This study determined the status of the learning environment of the public elementary and secondary schools in Malinao District School Year 2024 to 2025. Specifically, it answered the following sub-problems:

What are the areas of the learning environment that are provided in Malinao District?

What is the extent of provision of the learning environment along learners' safety and security; fair learning environment; management of classroom structure and activities; support for learners' participation; and management of learners' behavior?

Is there a significant difference on the extent of provision of the learning environment between the elementary and secondary teachers along the above-mentioned areas?

What are the challenges that affect the provision of the learning environment in Malinao District? and

What intervention plan on learning environment may be proposed to address the challenges?

This research study used the descriptive-survey method of research. This thesis followed the survey design since it gathered large amount of data from a limited group of respondents. A researcher-made questionnaire which was validated by the members of the Thesis Committee and two (2) external validators is the main tool in gathering the data from 226 elementary and secondary teachers of Malinao District. The following statistical measures were employed: frequency counts, percentage, weighted mean and F-test.

Keywords: Learning Environment; Extent of Provision; Areas; Learner Safety and Security

1. Introduction

In the world of education, it is a realization that learning will be successful in a positive and enriching school environment. As a result, more and more efforts are exerted to provide learning spaces that promote active interaction and a sense of community that enable formal and informal learning. Even the concept of learning environment which traditionally suggests only a place and space, educators consider the 21st learning environment to include a virtual, online and remote learning systems. This covers all conditions in which people learn best. In addition, modern learning spaces support positive human relationships needed for effective learning with new appropriate tools and structures that inspire the learners and education to achieve the 21st century knowledge and skills.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) focused on the learning needs around the globe in recommending that schools accommodate both the known and identifiable needs of today and the uncertain demands

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of the future. The schools should provide an environment that enhance learning process, encourage innovation and foster positive human relationships. Relative to the this, learning spaces will not all look alike. Since the educational needs differ from one context to the other.

Ensuring quality education goes beyond access to schools; it also involves creating an environment that fosters meaningful learning experiences. A well-structured and engaging learning environment plays a crucial role in student development, allowing learners to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. The Philippine Government in its pursuit to provide quality education for all initiated a lot of educational reforms and initiatives. This is in consonance to Article XIV, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution that mandates: *The State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.*

The above development includes the role of the teachers in transforming the educational landscape so that the objectives of the K to 12 programs are realized. The provision underscores the importance of a strong educational foundation that caters to diverse learners, ensuring that students acquire essential skills and knowledge necessary for lifelong learning. A key aspect of achieving this goal is the creation of an effective learning environment—one that is inclusive, responsive, and conducive to student engagement. In addition, the preparation of teachers and educators to deliver the needed competencies and practices are strongly encouraged. The Department of Education issued Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 42, series of 2017 to provide a basis for all learning and development programs for teachers in the implementation of the program. The National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) builds upon the principle that quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching.

There are seven (7) domains that include various strands which specify the practices of teachers. One of these domains is Learning Environment that encompasses six (6) strands. It highlights the role of teachers to provide learning environments that are safe, secure, fair and supportive in order to promote learner responsibility and achievement. Furthermore, it centers on creating an environment that is learning-focused and in which teachers efficiently manage learner behavior in a physical and virtual space. It highlights the need for teachers to utilize a range of resources and provide intellectually challenging and stimulating activities to encourage constructive classroom interactions geared towards the attainment of high standards of learning.

Learning environment represents not only the physical aspects of the school but other components such as processes, relationships and the shared values that enhance learning engagement and inclusion. It includes the surrounding environment, content, human resources and mutual relations. The physical space in which education takes place in today's school in the context of the content reform forming and implementing the competence-based curricula is really being diversified. This is not only the classroom itself. Learning now takes place in the school library, school yard, the nearby community, the city park and many other areas. The arrangement of the classroom allows changing quickly the pupils' working forms: in groups, individual work, the whole class work using diverse learning materials, including the digital, internet, mobile phones.

There are many changes in the learning environment, particularly in the Malinao District. These improvements stem from the strong commitment of educators in the Albay Division and Malinao District, supported by the strategic leadership and active involvement of various education stakeholders. However, despite these efforts, Malinao still faces challenges. In terms of physical infrastructure, while some school buildings have been renovated or newly constructed to accommodate the growing number of learners, many facilities remain inadequate and in need of further development.

However, even with the above scenarios, there are still a lot of areas that need to be considered to achieve the expected education outcomes in Malinao District. Afterall, there is no perfect learning environment. There is a continuous process of transformation in the learning environment as the people and immediate environment change and evolve. There is no longer one correct way of how and what to teach. The learning environment should be formed so that it would support different ways of learning – discussions, empirical inquiry, and reflection. This is one of the motivations of the researcher in conducting this study. The researcher wants to present the status of the learning environment of Malinao District to understand better how this aspect contributes in school success. Likewise, this study may provide current data on the learning environment of Malinao District that support the projects, programs and activities of the schools in the municipality so that there will be a conducive learning environment for the learners. Thus, this study was conducted.

2. Findings

The salient findings of the study are:

- The area with the highest average frequency on the areas of the learning environment provided in Malinao District as rated by the elementary and secondary teachers of Malinao District is obtained in management of classroom structure and activities with 111 or 98.13 %. It is followed by management of learner behavior with 106.5 or 84.46 %; then support for learner participation with 104 or 92.02 %; learner safety and security with an average of 95.5 or 85.04 %. The area with the lowest average of 89 or 79.72 % is in fair learning environment.
- The combined ratings of the elementary and secondary teachers in Malinao District on the extent of provision of the learning environment showed that there are four (4) areas with an adjectival description of always. The area with the highest combined rating of 4.43 is computed in support for learner participation. It is followed by fair learning environment with 4.40. Then, trailed by management of learners' behavior with 4.22 and classroom structure and activities with 4.20. The area with the lowest rating of 4.10 is obtained in learners' safety and security. The extent of provision of the learning environment along the five (5) areas covered in this study as rated by the elementary and secondary teachers has an over-all average of 4.27 with an adjectival description of always.
- The computed F values along the five (5) areas are the following. In learners' safety and security, the value is 0.118; along fair learning environment, the value is 1.192; along classroom structure and activities, the computed F value is 0.437; then, in support for learner's participation, the value is 0.019 and lastly in management of learner's behavior, the F computed value is 0.031. All these computed F values are very much lower when compared with the F tabular value of 5.318.
- The challenges with a rank of first along the five (5) areas of the study are: along learners' safety and security with a sum of rank of 2 and final rank of first is lack of financial resources; along fair learning environment, the challenge with a sum of rank of 2 and final rank of first is shortage of seminars and training on modern classroom assessment. In the area of classroom structure and activities, the challenge with a sun of rank of 2 and final rank of first is poor quality of infrastructural conditions in the classroom. In the area support for learners' participation, the challenge with the sum of rank of 2 and final rank of fist lack of social spaces necessary for interaction with their peers. Along management of xiii learners' behavior, the challenge with a sum of rank of 2 and final rank of first is big class size.
- An intervention plan may address the challenges that affect the provision of the learning environment in Malinao District.

3. Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher obtained the following conclusions:

- The area in learning environment most provided by elementary and secondary teachers in Malinao District is management of classroom structure and activities. The area in learning environment provided in Malinao District with the lowest number of teachers who observed is fair learning environment.
- The school heads and the teachers always provide the learning environment along support for learners' participation, fair learning environment, management of learners' behavior, classroom structure and activities while they often provide learners' safety and security.
- There is no significant difference on the extent of provision of the learning environment along learners' safety and security, fair learning environment, classroom structure and activities, support for learner's participation and management of learners' behavior between the elementary and secondary teachers of Malinao District.
- The top challenges on the provision of learning environment in Malinao District in the area of learners' safety and security is lack of financial resources; in fair learning environment, it is shortage of seminars and trainings on modern classroom assessment; in the area of classroom structure and activities, it is poor quality of infrastructural conditions in the classroom; in the area which is support for learners' participation, it is lack of social spaces necessary for interaction with their peers; and finally, in management of learners' behavior, it is big class size.
- The intervention plan when implemented may address the challenges in the provision of learning environment in Malinao District.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

- Extra efforts must be exerted by the school heads and teachers in the elementary and secondary schools of Malinao District to provide fair learning environment by being transparent and accountable in the delivery of education services. Common standards in assessment must be established.
- Activities related to the provision of support for learners' participation, fair learning environment, management of learners' behavior, classroom structure and activities must be sustained. On the other hand, school heads and teachers need to formulate standardized policies in assessment of performance of learners and teachers. These policies must be communicated to concerned parties.
- Programs that will involve the elementary and secondary teachers in Malinao District may be maintained by the Public Schools District Supervisor and encourage all teachers to participate and engage in these programs.
- The school heads and the Public Schools District Supervisor be provided with the list of challenges identified in this study for discussion and consideration.
- The researcher with the support of the school heads may implement the intervention to improve the provision of quality learning environments in Malinao District.

Areas for Further Study

- The researcher suggests the following topics that may help future researchers in the conduct of their study:
- A Phenomenological Study on the Effects of Learning Environment in Secondary Schools of Albay;
- The Perceptions of Junior High School Students on the Learning Environment in Malinao District;
- The Classroom Management Practices of Elementary Teachers in Malinao District.

4. Conclusion

The Learning Environment domain emerges as a crucial area in understanding and enhancing educational outcomes in the Malinao District. While progress has been made, the study recognizes that a truly effective learning environment goes beyond physical infrastructure—it must also foster positive relationships, inclusivity, and active learner engagement. Given the evolving demands of 21st-century education, assessing the current conditions of learning spaces is essential. This study seeks to provide relevant data and insights that highlight the role of the learning environment in shaping student success, thereby supporting informed decision-making and the development of more responsive programs in the district. Through this, the researcher aims to contribute meaningfully to the continuous improvement of school administration and educational quality in Malinao.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest should be disclosed

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